

A Comparative Study of Machine Learning Algorithms for Anomaly Detection in Industrial Environments: Performance and Environmental Impact

Álvaro Huertas-García¹[0000-0003-2165-0144], Carlos Martí-González¹[0009-0003-1387-1630], Rubén García Maezo¹[0000-0001-9500-3121], and Alejandro Echeverría Rey¹[0000-0003-3721-3459]

Department of Artificial Intelligence, FUNDITEC, C/ Faraday 7, Campus de Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid

{ahuertas, cmarti, rugarcia, aecheverria}@funditec.es

Abstract. This research explores the intersection of artificial intelligence and environmental sustainability, specifically in the context of anomaly detection in Industry 4.0. The study evaluates a range of machine learning algorithms and various configurations of Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), using several metrics to assess model performance alongside their environmental footprint. Findings show that traditional algorithms such as Decision Trees and Random Forests offer reliable efficiency and performance. In contrast, optimised MLP configurations can yield superior results, albeit with greater resource consumption. The research underscores the importance of balancing performance, complexity, and environmental impact in model development. Through a multi-objective optimization approach based on Pareto optimality principles, it reveals trade-offs between model performance and environmental considerations. The study thus serves as a guide for creating environmentally responsible machine learning models for industrial applications.

Keywords: Anomaly Detection · Green AI · Machine Learning · Artificial Intelligence · Industrial Environments · Environmental Impact

1 Introduction

Industry 4.0, a key player in the ongoing digital transformation, has considerably transformed various economic sectors, especially the industrial domain [1]. Fundamental to this transformation is the vast volume of data generated by diverse sensors embedded in industrial processes. When meticulously exploited, this data can significantly augment process monitoring, optimization, equipment integrity, and worker safety, while concurrently curbing operational costs [2].

Despite these potential benefits, the sheer magnitude and complexity of the data introduces significant challenges, particularly in identifying anomalies, which could signal critical issues or inefficiencies [3]. Even though machine learning,

a subset of AI, has shown promise in detecting these anomalies [4], its broad adoption in real-world manufacturing contexts is still met with substantial obstacles [1,4].

One significant hurdle, the focus of this study, is the environmental impact of AI operations. The high computational demands of machine learning lead to substantial energy consumption and consequential environmental effects [5]. This concern has fueled the emergence of 'Green AI,' a field striving to create AI solutions that balance effectiveness and environmental sustainability.

With industries worldwide seeking to diminish their carbon footprints, this study underscores the importance of considering both the effectiveness and environmental impact of AI systems designed for industrial management and optimization. It is in this industrial context that the study seeks to apply valuable, preprocessed data from an anomaly detection scenario for evaluating machine learning models for anomaly detection and classification.

Utilizing valuable anomaly detection data, the study performs a comparative analysis of machine learning and deep learning models, measuring performance and environmental parameters. The objectives are exploring algorithm-environment synergies and formulating best practices to advance industrial Green AI [1].

2 Related Works

Interest is growing in understanding and reducing the environmental footprint of AI systems [6,7]. Traditionally, AI research has prioritized accuracy over efficiency [8]. However, energy efficiency is now recognized as critical for scalability and real-world deployment [9]. This has paved the way for Green AI field, promoting environmentally sustainable AI technologies [1,2].

Multiple Green AI approaches have emerged. Schwartz et al. [5] advocate evaluating efficiency alongside accuracy, considering financial costs to establish efficiency baselines. Patterson et al. [10] outline best practices to reduce AI emissions through efficient hardware usage, energy-efficient models, transparency, and renewable energy. Data and model modifications also show promise, like carefully altering datasets to cut energy consumption up to 92.16% without sacrificing accuracy [11]. Profiling inference task energy use is another valuable technique [12].

Selecting efficient algorithms tailored to the use case is also key but understudied. It has been demonstrated [13] that lightweight algorithms like ARIMA, Random Forest, and Gradient Boosting improved efficiency for security-focused CSIRTs, revealing the importance of model choice aligning efficiency, performance, and industrial applicability.

New trends of Large Language Models (e.g. GPT-3) [14] present computational and energy challenges. Quantization to reduce memory and computations shows potential to lower inference energy needs [9,15]. Additionally, dimensionality reduction also helps large models to obtain substantial reductions in dimensions, storage and faster fitting times without sacrificing performance [16]. Finally,

comparative analysis of machine learning techniques are promising as can reveal optimization opportunities [17].

Gaps remain despite growing Green AI interest. The focus is often on deep learning instead of traditional machine learning [10], especially for industrial use cases like anomaly detection which could benefit from optimized traditional technique. Further work is needed to holistically improve efficiency across AI systems.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data

The data employed in this research originate from an industrial milling machine. The dataset, curated and labeled under expert supervision, consists of 308,772 instances representing 30-second measurement windows from sensors monitoring temperature, vibrations, and current. These instances present a three-class imbalanced problem, categorized into non-anomalous states (99.86%), single sensor anomalies (0.01%), and multiple sensor anomalies (0.13%).

The data engineering phase involved the transformation of each 30-second interval of sensor readings into a comprehensive set of features using descriptive statistical calculations, including mean, maximum, minimum, kurtosis, skewness, and the number of current peaks. This procedure expanded the initial 7-feature dataset into one comprising 38 features, yielding a detailed view of the machine's operation across each time interval. Any missing numerical values were handled through mean imputation.

However, due to multicollinearity, features with correlations above a threshold of 0.9 were eliminated to prevent potential negative impacts on the machine learning models. This primarily affected the current and vibration sensor readings, reducing the feature set from 38 to a more manageable 25.

For the machine learning model development phase, the focus was on ensuring performance and reproducibility. The random seed value was set to 1794 consistently across all experiments. To prevent overfitting and underfitting, the stratified Kfold method with ten folds was used for cross-validation. The data was divided such that 70% was used for training and validation, while the remaining 30% was set aside as a holdout test set for the final model evaluation."

3.2 Machine Learning Algorithms

This study implemented a diverse spectrum of machine learning algorithms to provide unique insights into anomaly detection within a Green AI framework [18]. Linear models such as Logistic Regression offer interpretability and foundational understanding of the dataset's basic patterns [19]. Non-linear techniques like K-Nearest Neighbors capture intricate relationships overlooked by linear models [20]. Decision tree models effectively handle categorical and numerical data while remaining interpretable [19], [21].

Table 1: MLP Configurations and Parameters

Model	Config	Parameters
MLP_1	100	2903
MLP_2	100, 70	9883
MLP_3	100, 70, 50	13373
MLP_4	100, 70, 50, 20	14303
MLP_5	50	1453
MLP_6	50, 50	4003
MLP_7	200	5803
MLP_8	200, 100	25603
MLP_9	50, 40, 30, 20	5253
MLP_10	40, 10	1483

Ensemble methods like Random Forest improve robustness by aggregating multiple decision trees, proving valuable for complex data [19], [18]. Boosting techniques iteratively refine decision-making, suiting demanding anomaly detection [18], [22].

Multi-Layer Perceptrons leverage neural networks to learn complex feature relationships by adjusting weights, making them versatile for this task [18], [23]. To evaluate Green AI goals, MLPs were explored with CPU and GPU using quantization to contrast precision and efficiency [24].

This diversity of algorithms, each with different strengths, provides a comprehensive framework for investigating anomaly detection. Linear techniques establish a foundation before non-linear and ensemble methods capture greater complexity. Boosting refines decision-making while MLPs learn intricate relationships. Together, these models enable a nuanced Green AI analysis. Specific configurations are detailed in the Experimental Setup 3.4.

3.3 Computational Resources

As part of our commitment to Green AI principles, we strive to provide transparency and clarity regarding the computational resources used in this study. In addition to advocating energy-efficient AI solutions, these principles also emphasize the importance of reporting the resources necessary to reproduce the results of a study.

The key software utilized includes the Linux operating system (v5.15.107+) providing the foundation; Python 3.10.11 [25] as the core programming language; Scikit-learn 1.2.2 [26] and PyCaret 3.0.2 [27] for implementing machine learning models; CodeCarbon 2.2.1¹ for emissions tracking; and PyTorch 2.0.1 [28] with PyTorch Lightning² to enable modular deep learning and quantization for

¹ <https://codecarbon.io/>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/3828935>

Multi-Layer Perceptrons aligned with Green AI principles. This software stack enabled efficient model training, evaluation, and optimization while adhering to reproducibility and transparency standards.

The hardware enabling efficient model training and evaluation comprised a 2-core Intel Xeon CPU @ 2.20GHz allowing concurrent multi-threading; 12GB RAM to handle large datasets and models while sustaining multiple tasks; and a Tesla T4 GPU leveraged for highly parallel deep learning training. The CPU executed most models, while the GPU's parallelism accelerated Multi-Layer Perceptrons.

All machine learning models were executed on the CPU, with the exception of the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). In our study, the MLP was unique in its use of both the CPU and GPU. This utilization of the GPU allowed us to explore its potential for accelerating deep learning tasks, demonstrating the resource efficiencies achievable in this field. Such details underscore Green AI's transparency and provide a comprehensive picture of the resources necessary to replicate our study.

3.4 Experimental Setup

The experimental setup outlined in this section incorporates traditional machine learning models and Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs). The aim is to generate robust, reproducible results in adherence to Green AI principles.

A range of machine learning models, complemented by different MLPs configurations, is utilized with default parameters from the Scikit-learn library and a fixed random state seed (1794) for reproducibility. The MLP's configuration considered are depicted in Table 1. These configurations include only linear layers with no batch normalization or dropout layers, utilizing the rectified linear unit (ReLU) as the activation function.

The assessment for model performance and environmental impact comprised CO2 equivalent (CO2eq) emissions, total energy consumption by CPU, GPU, and RAM (expressed in kW), the F1 Macro score, and the elapsed time during both training and inference stages. This approach ensures that we maintain a balance between resource efficiency and model performance, upholding the principles of Green AI. To ensure reliability, each model is run five times, with the average values and standard deviations calculated for all critical measurements.

The top-performing MLP model undergoes dynamic quantization with PyTorch and PyTorch Lightning, aiming to minimize model size and maximize computational speed. This process entails the determination of scale factors based on observed runtime data ranges, conversion of model parameters to int8 beforehand, and the execution of arithmetic operations using vectorized int8 instructions.

3.5 Multi-Objective Comparison

To evaluate the balance between environmental impact and performance, a multi-objective optimization approach was adopted. The F1 Macro score was minimized using its reciprocal to enable Pareto analysis.

The computed Pareto front shows non-dominated solutions representing ideal trade-offs between impact and performance. A two-dimensional optimization using CO₂ equivalent and F1 Macro score was performed first, as CO₂ is a key environmental metric. A subsequent multi-objective optimization incorporated all factors: time, energy, CO₂, and performance. This comprehensive evaluation revealed intricate trade-offs relevant to optimizing machine learning models.

3.6 Limitations

While striving to implement a comprehensive selection of algorithms suitable for industrial anomaly detection, certain methods and parameter configurations were unavoidably excluded due to computational constraints. Though default values provided an evaluative baseline, a lack of exhaustive hyperparameter optimization may have precluded peak algorithm performance. Omitting aspects such as dropout and batch normalization in the MLP models may have also impacted results, albeit favorably curtailing resource consumption. Moreover, inherent data imbalances could influence outcome precision, despite mitigation efforts. While acknowledged limitations impart transparency and illuminate avenues for future work, the study maintains substantive contributions to the emerging domain of environmentally responsible machine learning. These recognized limitations not only provide transparency but also delineate potential directions for future research, contributing to the broader discourse of Green AI.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Performance and Environmental Impact of Machine Learning Models

As shown in Table 2, during the training and cross-validation phases, the Decision Tree and Random Forest Classifiers stood out for their exceptional performance, boasting F1 Macro scores of 0.9101 and 0.9335, respectively. These models completed these phases with high efficiency, minimizing time taken, CO₂ emissions, and energy consumption. The Extreme Gradient Boosting model also achieved a notable F1 Macro score of 0.9235, albeit with greater time and energy expenditure.

Contrarily, the K Neighbors Classifier (KNN) consumed significant resources without delivering high performance, reaching only a 0.6163 F1 Macro score. Naive Bayes and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis models also lagged in performance, failing to offer substantial improvements in time efficiency, CO₂ equivalent, or energy consumption.

In the inference and cross-validation phase (see Table 3), the trends generally remained consistent. The Decision Tree and Random Forest Classifiers again

Table 2: Duration, Emission, Energy and Performance in Training and Cross Validation phase for Machine Learning algorithms.

Model	Time (s)	CO2 equivalent (Kg)	Energy Consumed (KW)	F1 Macro
ADA	20.98 ± 15.91	3.29E-04 ± 2.49E-04	7.27E-04 ± 5.51E-04	0.6827
DT	9.03 ± 2.16	1.42E-04 ± 3.40E-05	3.13E-04 ± 7.50E-05	0.9101
ET	18.85 ± 13.13	2.96E-04 ± 2.06E-04	6.53E-04 ± 4.55E-04	0.7686
KNN	365.78 ± 3.78	5.73E-03 ± 5.90E-05	1.27E-02 ± 1.31E-04	0.6163
LDA	8.79 ± 0.65	1.38E-04 ± 1.00E-05	3.05E-04 ± 2.30E-05	0.7303
LGBM	17.15 ± 2.80	2.69E-04 ± 4.40E-05	5.94E-04 ± 9.70E-05	0.5517
LR	17.79 ± 12.42	2.79E-04 ± 1.95E-04	6.16E-04 ± 4.30E-04	0.6679
NB	8.50 ± 1.04	1.33E-0 ± 1.60E-05	2.94E-04 ± 3.60E-05	0.3953
QDA	8.31 ± 1.05	1.30E-04 ± 1.60E-05	2.88E-04 ± 3.60E-05	0.364
RF	16.78 ± 11.29	2.63E-04 ± 1.77E-04	5.81E-04 ± 3.91E-04	0.9335
RC	7.41 ± 0.64	1.16E-04 ± 1.00E-05	2.57E-04 ± 2.20E-05	0.6265
SVM	8.22 ± 1.33	1.29E-04 ± 2.10E-05	2.85E-04 ± 4.60E-05	0.6313
XGB	20.62 ± 22.75	3.23E-04 ± 3.57E-04	7.14E-04 ± 7.88E-04	0.9235

excelled in performance and efficiency. The KNN classifier, however, continued to struggle, consuming the most resources without substantial improvement in the F1 Macro score.

From the findings, a trade-off between performance and environmental impact is apparent. The Decision Tree and Random Forest Classifiers demonstrate the possibility of high performance with reduced environmental impact.

Comparing the single tree Decision Tree Classifier with the ensemble-based Random Forest Classifier reveals the balance between performance and computational cost. The latter, with its enhanced accuracy from multiple decision trees, outperforms the former but at higher computational requirements. Particularly during inference, where speed is often crucial, the Decision Tree model is inherently more efficient due to its simpler structure. Notably, its lower computational demand results in less energy use and CO₂ emissions, making it a more eco-friendly choice. Future work can explore enhancing efficiency in high-performing models and improving performance in energy-efficient ones.

4.2 Performance and Environmental Impact of MLPs

As observed in Tables 4 and 5, during the training and cross-validation phase for MLPs, we observed an interesting balance between model complexity, performance, and resource efficiency. Simpler configurations, such as MLP_5 with 50 nodes in a single layer, were more time-efficient and consumed less energy across both CPU and GPU platforms. However, more complex configurations, like MLP_8 with

Table 3: Duration, Emission, Energy and Performance in Inference phase for Machine Learning algorithms

Model	Time (s)	CO2 equivalent (Kg)	Energy Consumed (KW)	F1 Macro
ADA	3.80 ± 0.33	6.00E-05 ± 5.10E-06	1.32E-04 ± 1.13E-05	0.6537
DT	2.48 ± 0.02	3.90E-05 ± 3.44E-07	8.60E-05 ± 7.59E-07	0.899
ET	3.76 ± 0.66	5.90E-05 ± 1.04E-05	1.30E-04 ± 2.30E-05	0.7103
KNN	172.78 ± 0.34	2.71E-03 ± 5.12E-06	5.98E-03 ± 1.13E-05	0.595
LDA	2.73 ± 0.23	4.30E-05 ± 3.61E-06	9.50E-05 ± 7.97E-06	0.695
LGBM	4.98 ± 0.49	7.80E-05 ± 7.74E-06	1.73E-04 ± 1.71E-05	0.5907
LR	2.54 ± 0.01	4.00E-05 ± 2.51E-07	8.80E-05 ± 5.54E-07	0.6548
NB	2.54 ± 0.09	4.00E-05 ± 1.43E-06	8.80E-05 ± 3.16E-06	0.3904
QDA	2.62 ± 0.03	4.10E-05 ± 4.87E-07	9.10E-05 ± 1.08E-06	0.4734
RF	3.53 ± 0.42	5.50E-05 ± 6.64E-06	1.22E-04 ± 1.47E-05	0.9137
RC	2.60 ± 0.42	4.10E-05 ± 6.54E-06	9.00E-05 ± 1.44E-05	0.595
SVM	2.41 ± 0.01	3.80E-05 ± 1.57E-07	8.30E-05 ± 3.46E-07	0.5703
XGB	2.86 ± 0.03	4.50E-05 ± 4.98E-07	9.90E-05 ± 1.10E-06	0.8949

Table 4: Duration, Emission, Energy and Performance in Training and Cross Validation phase for Multi Perceptron Model deep learning model with CPU

Model	Time (s)	CO2 equivalent (Kg)	Energy Consumed (KW)	F1 Macro
MLP_1	501.15 ± 217.05	1.44E-03 ± 6.22E-04	6.57E-03 ± 2.85E-03	0.6855
MLP_2	824.03 ± 361.06	2.36E-03 ± 1.03E-03	1.08E-02 ± 4.74E-03	0.6807
MLP_3	1303.34 ± 574.55	3.74E-03 ± 1.65E-03	1.71E-02 ± 7.54E-03	0.6578
MLP_4	1317.20 ± 581.43	3.78E-03 ± 1.67E-03	1.73E-02 ± 7.63E-03	0.6273
MLP_5	204.99 ± 84.56	5.87E-04 ± 2.42E-04	2.69E-03 ± 1.11E-03	0.7068
MLP_6	535.39 ± 232.56	1.53E-03 ± 6.67E-04	7.02E-03 ± 3.05E-03	0.6394
MLP_7	789.98 ± 346.03	2.26E-03 ± 9.92E-04	1.04E-02 ± 4.54E-03	0.6786
MLP_8	2470.65 ± 1097.28	7.08E-03 ± 3.14E-03	3.24E-02 ± 1.44E-02	0.7098
MLP_9	794.30 ± 348.35	2.28E-03 ± 9.98E-04	1.04E-02 ± 4.57E-03	0.6479
MLP_10	220.22 ± 91.62	6.31E-04 ± 2.63E-04	2.89E-03 ± 1.20E-03	0.6986

Table 5: Duration, Emission, Energy and Performance in Training and Cross Validation phase for Multi Perceptron Model deep learning model with GPU

Model	Time (s)	CO2 equivalent (Kg)	Energy Consumed (KW)	F1 Macro
MLP_1	404.78 ± 175.32	2.42E-03 ± 1.05E-03	6.37E-03 ± 2.76E-03	0.6855
MLP_2	665.94 ± 291.95	3.99E-03 ± 1.75E-03	1.05E-02 ± 4.60E-03	0.6807
MLP_3	1015.74 ± 448.64	6.09E-03 ± 2.69E-03	1.61E-02 ± 7.09E-03	0.6578
MLP_4	1051.51 ± 464.61	6.28E-03 ± 2.78E-03	1.65E-02 ± 7.31E-03	0.6273
MLP_5	184.74 ± 76.64	1.10E-03 ± 4.56E-04	2.90E-03 ± 1.20E-03	0.7068
MLP_6	420.28 ± 182.31	2.51E-03 ± 1.09E-03	6.62E-03 ± 2.87E-03	0.6394
MLP_7	621.77 ± 272.29	3.71E-03 ± 1.62E-03	9.77E-03 ± 4.28E-03	0.6786
MLP_8	1970.52 ± 875.20	1.17E-02 ± 5.22E-03	3.09E-02 ± 1.37E-02	0.7098
MLP_9	670.54 ± 294.59	4.01E-03 ± 1.76E-03	1.06E-02 ± 4.65E-03	0.6479
MLP_10	181.83 ± 76.03	1.09E-03 ± 4.54E-04	2.86E-03 ± 1.20E-03	0.6986

two layers and 300 nodes, delivered higher F1 Macro scores, despite consuming more resources. This points to a clear trade-off between performance and resource efficiency during training.

In the inference phase (see Tables 6 and 7), similar trends persisted. Complex configurations like MLP_4 and MLP_7 exhibited higher F1 Macro scores, albeit at the cost of more time and energy. Conversely, simpler configurations, despite their lower F1 scores, failed to show significant improvement in time efficiency or energy consumption. These findings again highlight the trade-off between performance and complexity in MLPs, pointing towards the need for optimization strategies to balance performance and efficiency.

When examining the effects of quantization in Table 8, significant efficiency improvements were noted in the quantized (int8) MLP5 model on CPU, with reduced training time, CO₂ emissions, and energy consumption compared to the original (fp32) model. Notably, this did not compromise performance, as F1 Macro scores and validation loss values remained consistent across all configurations. This demonstrates the potential of quantization for enhancing the efficiency of machine learning models without sacrificing performance. Future investigations could further explore the impact of quantization on various MLP configurations and tasks.

4.3 Metrics Evaluation Comparison

The evaluation and comparison of various performance metrics provided valuable insights into model capabilities for anomaly detection. Metrics like F1 Macro (0.9137 for Random Forest), MCC (0.8016 for MLP_5), and Kappa (0.8073 for Random Forest) effectively assessed prediction quality and class differentiation, while AUC (0.9961 for XGBoost) identified true positives - critical for anomaly

Table 6: Duration, Emission, Energy and Performance in Inference phase for Multi Perceptron Model deep learning model with CPU

Model	Time (s)	CO2 equivalent (Kg)	Energy Consumed (KW)	F1 Macro
MLP_1	6.94 ± 1.31	2.00E-05 ± 4.00E-06	9.10E-05 ± 1.70E-05	0.6578
MLP_2	6.59 ± 1.04	1.90E-05 ± 3.00E-06	8.60E-05 ± 1.40E-05	0.5992
MLP_3	5.80 ± 0.86	1.70E-05 ± 2.00E-06	7.60E-05 ± 1.10E-05	0.5992
MLP_4	7.39 ± 1.32	2.10E-05 ± 4.00E-06	9.70E-05 ± 1.70E-05	0.7031
MLP_5	6.30 ± 1.14	1.80E-05 ± 3.00E-06	8.30E-05 ± 1.50E-05	0.7144
MLP_6	7.10 ± 1.59	2.00E-05 ± 5.00E-06	9.30E-05 ± 2.10E-05	0.5992
MLP_7	6.83 ± 1.18	2.00E-05 ± 3.00E-06	9.00E-05 ± 1.50E-05	0.7143
MLP_8	8.76 ± 1.70	2.50E-05 ± 5.00E-06	1.15E-04 ± 2.20E-05	0.5978
MLP_9	6.57 ± 1.03	1.90E-05 ± 3.00E-06	8.60E-05 ± 1.40E-05	0.6598
MLP_10	6.56 ± 1.38	1.90E-05 ± 4.00E-06	8.60E-05 ± 1.80E-05	0.5992

detection. Models optimizing these metrics exhibited well-rounded performance. However, Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 had limitations in imbalanced datasets, requiring careful interpretation despite high scores (0.9995 for MLP_10).

Overall, the analysis revealed that while metrics provide crucial performance insights, careful selection aligned with the anomaly detection task is vital. AUC, F1 Macro, MCC and Kappa should take priority over Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1. Comparing models should also consider the metrics showing strength in complex pattern recognition, classification, and true positive identification - not just aggregate scores. Additionally, simple models occasionally optimized certain metrics but underperformed holistically. Thus, utilizing a range of well-chosen, informative metrics while evaluating trade-offs can promote effective anomaly detection and avoid pitfalls from improperly assessed models.

4.4 Comparative Analysis and Key Observations

The performance comparison between classic machine learning models and MLPs yields some interesting insights. Among the classic machine learning models, the Decision Tree and Random Forest classifiers proved to be the most effective, achieving high F1 Macro scores. Their superiority could be attributed to their inherent ability to handle both linear and non-linear data, making them versatile and efficient across diverse data sets.

On the other hand, the MLPs showed potential for even higher performance, but the results were contingent on the configurations used. More complex configurations, despite being resource-intensive, delivered superior F1 Macro scores, indicating a trade-off between model complexity and performance. It's worth noting that while these configurations required more computational resources,

Table 7: Duration, Emission, Energy and Performance in Inference phase for Multi Perceptron Model deep learning model with GPU

Model	Time (s)	CO2 equivalent (Kg)	Energy Consumed (KW)	F1 Macro
MLP_1	4.46 ± 0.75	2.70E-05 ± 4.49E-06	7.00E-05 ± 1.18E-05	0.6578
MLP_2	2.85 ± 0.04	1.70E-05 ± 2.45E-07	4.50E-05 ± 6.45E-07	0.5992
MLP_3	4.77 ± 0.78	2.80E-05 ± 4.68E-06	7.50E-05 ± 1.23E-05	0.5992
MLP_4	5.17 ± 0.44	3.10E-05 ± 2.67E-06	8.20E-05 ± 7.03E-06	0.7031
MLP_5	5.07 ± 0.88	3.00E-05 ± 5.33E-06	8.00E-05 ± 1.41E-05	0.7144
MLP_6	4.12 ± 0.58	2.50E-05 ± 3.38E-06	6.50E-05 ± 8.90E-06	0.5992
MLP_7	2.84 ± 0.06	1.70E-05 ± 4.03E-07	4.50E-05 ± 1.06E-06	0.7143
MLP_8	4.22 ± 0.58	2.50E-05 ± 3.40E-06	6.60E-05 ± 8.96E-06	0.5978
MLP_9	5.71 ± 0.91	3.40E-05 ± 5.47E-06	9.00E-05 ± 1.44E-05	0.6598
MLP_10	4.70 ± 0.74	2.80E-05 ± 4.43E-06	7.40E-05 ± 1.17E-05	0.5992

Table 8: Comparison of MLP_5 model in quantized int8 and float 32 CPU and GPU precision at Inference phase.

Model	Size (KB)	Time (s)	CO2 equivalent (Kg)	Energy Consumed (KW)	F1 Macro
int8_cpu	4.6	5.63 ± 0.88	5.66E-05 ± 9.00E-06	1.16E-04 ± 1.80E-05	0.7223
fp32_cpu	7.6	6.30 ± 1.14	6.32E-05 ± 5.33E-06	1.29E-04 ± 1.41E-05	0.7223
fp32_gpu	7.6	8.34 ± 0.42	8.40E-05 ± 1.89E-06	1.72E-04 ± 9.00E-06	0.7223

Fig. 1: Two-dimensional Pareto front demonstrating the trade-off between CO₂ equivalent (inverted and log-scaled on the X-axis) and F1 Macro score.

they didn't necessarily compromise on performance, maintaining comparable F1 Macro scores to those of simpler configurations.

In terms of environmental impact, the Decision Tree and Random Forest classifiers were observed to be the most efficient, with low time, CO₂ equivalent, and energy consumption values, while maintaining high performance scores. This efficiency could be linked to their inherent simplicity and lower computational complexity compared to other models like the K Neighbors Classifier and Extreme Gradient Boosting.

On the contrary, MLPs generally consumed more time and energy, especially when more complex configurations were used. However, the use of quantization significantly mitigated these effects, maintaining performance while reducing time, CO₂ emissions, and energy consumption on the CPU platform. Interestingly, despite leveraging GPU capabilities, the MLPs didn't show a significant reduction in their environmental impact, suggesting an area for future exploration in optimization of MLP configurations for GPU use.

The Pareto front, computed for both the two-dimensional Figure 1 and multi-objective scenarios Figure 2, revealed that the Decision Tree Classifier, Random Forest Classifier, Ridge Classifier, SVM Linear Kernel, and Linear Discriminant Analysis models presented the best compromise between high performance and low environmental impact. These models, found in the Pareto set, were not dominated by any other model, implying that no other model outperformed them across all objectives simultaneously.

However, the "best" model choice from the Pareto set depends on specific priorities and constraints. For instance, a model that minimizes CO₂ emissions might be preferred in contexts prioritizing environmental concerns, even at the cost of slight compromises on performance or longer computation time.

Thus, the Pareto front presents a range of optimal solutions, each aligning with different acceptable trade-offs between performance and environmental

Fig. 2: Three-dimensional Pareto front showcasing the trade-offs among CO₂ equivalent (inverted and log-scaled), F1 Macro score, and computation time.

impact. Future work could focus on further understanding these trade-offs and exploring strategies to extend the Pareto front, seeking higher performance with lower environmental impact.

5 Conclusion

This paper addresses the pressing need for a balance between environmental impact and performance in machine learning algorithms and Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) used for anomaly detection in industry. By evaluating models using both the F1 Macro score and a measure of environmental footprint (time duration, CO₂ equivalent, and energy consumed during training, cross-validation, and inference), the study highlights the efficiency-performance trade-off in these models.

Decision Trees and Random Forests have been identified as high performers with low resource consumption, whereas the K Neighbors Classifier, despite its resource intensity, showed less satisfactory performance. Models like Extreme Gradient Boosting showed high performance but at a significant resource cost. Simpler MLP configurations were found to be efficient, but their more complex counterparts provided higher performance, pointing to a trade-off between efficiency and complexity.

Using Pareto analysis, a compromise between model performance and environmental footprint was established, with Decision Tree Classifier, Random Forest Classifier, Ridge Classifier, SVM Linear Kernel, and Linear Discriminant Analysis emerging as optimal solutions. Still, the choice of the "best" model would be contingent upon the specific scenario, considering the variable weightage between performance and environmental impact.

Interestingly, while traditional algorithms remained robust performers, optimized MLPs demonstrated higher potential albeit with more resource consumption. Using GPUs instead of CPUs did not significantly improve MLP performance, hinting at future optimization avenues.

Implications of this research are substantial. The results underline the need to harmonize model performance, complexity, and environmental impact in machine learning. The study provides critical insights for future research aiming to develop machine learning models that are not only high performing but also environmentally friendly.

Acknowledgments

The Detecta project is co-financed by the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism of Spain through the line of support for Innovative Business Clusters, in its 2022 call for proposals under the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan.

References

1. R. S. Peres, X. Jia, J. Lee, K. Sun, A. W. Colombo, and J. Barata, "Industrial artificial intelligence in industry 4.0 - systematic review, challenges and outlook," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 220121–220139, 2020.
2. J. Lee, H. Davari, J. Singh, and V. Pandhare, "Industrial artificial intelligence for industry 4.0-based manufacturing systems," *Manufacturing Letters*, vol. 18, pp. 20–23, 2018.
3. H. Kim and T. Shon, "Industrial network-based behavioral anomaly detection in AI-enabled smart manufacturing," *The Journal of Supercomputing*, vol. 78, no. 11, pp. 13554–13563, 2022.
4. J. Audibert, P. Michiardi, F. Guyard, S. Marti, and M. A. Zuluaga, "Do deep neural networks contribute to multivariate time series anomaly detection?," *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 132, p. 108945, 2022.
5. R. Schwartz, J. Dodge, N. A. Smith, and O. Etzioni, "Green AI," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 63, p. 54–63, nov 2020.
6. T. Yigitcanlar, R. Mehmood, and J. M. Corchado, "Green artificial intelligence: Towards an efficient, sustainable and equitable technology for smart cities and futures," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 16, 2021.
7. D. Rolnick, P. L. Donti, L. H. Kaack, K. Kochanski, A. Lacoste, K. Sankaran, A. S. Ross, N. Milojevic-Dupont, N. Jaques, A. Waldman-Brown, A. S. Luccioni, T. Maharaj, E. D. Sherwin, S. K. Mukkavilli, K. P. Kording, C. P. Gomes, A. Y. Ng, D. Hassabis, J. C. Platt, F. Creutzig, J. Chayes, and Y. Bengio, "Tackling climate change with machine learning," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 55, feb 2022.
8. R. Nishant, M. Kennedy, and J. Corbett, "Artificial intelligence for sustainability: Challenges, opportunities, and a research agenda," *International Journal of Information Management*, vol. 53, p. 102104, 2020.
9. S. Kim, A. Gholami, Z. Yao, M. W. Mahoney, and K. Keutzer, "I-bert: Integer-only bert quantization," 2021.
10. D. Patterson, J. Gonzalez, U. Hölzle, Q. Le, C. Liang, L.-M. Munguia, D. Rothchild, D. R. So, M. Texier, and J. Dean, "The carbon footprint of machine learning training will plateau, then shrink," *Computer*, vol. 55, no. 7, pp. 18–28, 2022.

11. R. Verdecchia, L. Cruz, J. Sallou, M. Lin, J. Wickenden, and E. Hotellier, "Data-centric green AI an exploratory empirical study," in *2022 International Conference on ICT for Sustainability (ICT4S)*, IEEE, jun 2022.
12. S. Lahmer, A. Khoshsirat, M. Rossi, and A. Zanella, "Energy consumption of neural networks on nvidia edge boards: an empirical model," in *2022 20th International Symposium on Modeling and Optimization in Mobile, Ad hoc, and Wireless Networks (WiOpt)*, pp. 365–371, 2022.
13. R. G. Maezo and A. E. Rey, "Boosted csirt with ai powered open source framework," in *2023 JNIC Cybersecurity Conference (JNIC)*, pp. 1–8, IEEE, 2023.
14. T. B. Brown, B. Mann, N. Ryder, M. Subbiah, J. Kaplan, P. Dhariwal, A. Neelakantan, P. Shyam, G. Sastry, A. Askell, S. Agarwal, A. Herbert-Voss, G. Krueger, T. Henighan, R. Child, A. Ramesh, D. M. Ziegler, J. Wu, C. Winter, C. Hesse, M. Chen, E. Sigler, M. Litwin, S. Gray, B. Chess, J. Clark, C. Berner, S. McCandlish, A. Radford, I. Sutskever, and D. Amodei, "Language models are few-shot learners," 2020.
15. H. Wu, P. Judd, X. Zhang, M. Isaev, and P. Micikevicius, "Integer quantization for deep learning inference: Principles and empirical evaluation," 2020.
16. Á. Huertas-García, A. Martín, J. Huertas-Tato, and D. Camacho, "Exploring Dimensionality Reduction Techniques in Multilingual Transformers," *Cognitive Computation*, vol. 15, pp. 590–612, Mar. 2023.
17. U. Kanewala, S. Weerakoon, and R. Nawarathna, "Exploring deep learning and tree-based ensemble models for chiller energy consumption predictions," in *2021 IEEE 16th International Conference on Industrial and Information Systems (ICIIS)*, pp. 306–311, 2021.
18. A. B. Nassif, M. A. Talib, Q. Nasir, and F. M. Dakalbab, "Machine learning for anomaly detection: A systematic review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 78658–78700, 2021.
19. C. M. Bishop and N. M. Nasrabadi, *Pattern recognition and machine learning*, vol. 4. Springer, 2006.
20. E. Alpaydin, "Introduction to machine learning," in *Adaptive computation and machine learning*, 2004.
21. M. P. Deisenroth, A. A. Faisal, and C. S. Ong, "Mathematics for machine learning," 2020.
22. G. Ke, Q. Meng, T. Finley, T. Wang, W. Chen, W. Ma, Q. Ye, and T.-Y. Liu, "Lightgbm: A highly efficient gradient boosting decision tree," in *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems, NIPS'17*, (Red Hook, NY, USA), p. 3149–3157, Curran Associates Inc., 2017.
23. L. Van Efferen and A. M. Ali-Eldin, "A multi-layer perceptron approach for flow-based anomaly detection," in *2017 International Symposium on Networks, Computers and Communications (ISNCC)*, pp. 1–6, 2017.
24. H. Ma, H. Qiu, Y. Gao, Z. Zhang, A. Abuadbba, M. Xue, A. Fu, Z. Jiliang, S. Al-Sarawi, and D. Abbott, "Quantization backdoors to deep learning commercial frameworks," 2023.
25. G. Van Rossum and F. L. Drake, *Python 3 Reference Manual*. Scotts Valley, CA: CreateSpace, 2009.
26. F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and E. Duchesnay, "Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
27. M. Ali, *PyCaret: An open source, low-code machine learning library in Python*, April 2020. PyCaret version 1.0.

28. A. Paszke, S. Gross, F. Massa, A. Lerer, J. Bradbury, G. Chanan, T. Killeen, Z. Lin, N. Gimeshein, L. Antiga, A. Desmaison, A. Kopf, E. Yang, Z. DeVito, M. Raison, A. Tejani, S. Chilamkurthy, B. Steiner, L. Fang, J. Bai, and S. Chintala, “Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32*, pp. 8024–8035, Curran Associates, Inc., 2019.